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APPRAISAL OF THE LAWS ON PROSECUTION OF ELECTORAL OFFENCES IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Free, fair, peaceful and credible elections are the basic tenets of every Democracy all over the world. Short of these, the elections will not meet the standard thereby whittle down the essence of democracy and may result in the commission of electoral offences. Electoral offences are committed before, during and after elections. In Nigeria, the commission of these offences is in the increase yet there are few prosecutions. Offences like rigging, ballot box/BVAS (Bimodal Voter Automated System) snatching, killings, maiming, murder, arson etc. are in the increase in the successive elections. Sometimes, election officials and security agencies are complicit in the commission of these offences. There exist many laws conferring power on various institutions and/or persons to prosecute electoral offences like the Attorneys - General of the Federation and that of the states, the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC), the Nigeria Police, Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), Independent Corrupt Practices Commission (ICPC) and even private persons. This research sets to examine the lacunas associated with these laws on prosecution of electoral offences. This work adopted doctrinal method of research. The research recommended that Electoral Offences Commission should be

established and conferred with the power of arrest, detention, search, investigation and prosecution.

Keywords: Elections, prosecution, Electoral offences.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The commission of electoral offences is as old as Democracy itself in Nigeria. Therefore, the introduction of Democracy in Nigeria came with committing of electoral offences. Electoral offences are also crimes. The Commission of these offences is in the increase as most people committing this offence get away with it. It should be noted that unless they are dealt with seriously, the citizens may no longer have confidence in all the elections. Even the electoral umpire is worried about the situation¹. “That prosecution of electoral offenders in Nigeria is the most challenging tasks if not impossible despite the Laws on the prosecution of electoral offences”². Corroborating this position, the present chairman of the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) Prof. Mahmood Yakubu, said on 18th February, 2023 that “One of the numerous responsibilities carried out by the Commission is the prosecution of electoral offenders describing it as the most challenging duty for INEC. That the delay in the prosecution of electoral offenders has been one of the most challenging tasks for the commission since its establishment”³.

Indeed the problems associated with elections have direct impact on the performance of democratic institutions⁴. The Nigerian Government acknowledges that “controversies over highly rigged elections have been the forerunner to political violence and instability in Nigeria.”⁵ Acknowledging the position, Jega, A.M. former Chairman of the Independent National Electoral Commission of Nigeria (INEC) said:

“A series of badly conducted elections could create permanent political instability and easily reverse the gains of democratization... it can be argued

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¹ Lamenting about the the situation the INEC chairman, prof Mahmood Yakubu said

² Opera News.com, he said it on the 18th February, 2022 during a one day public hearng on the National Electoral Offences Commission (Establishment) Bill 2021 organized by the senate Committee on INECworkshop

³ Opera News.com, he said it on the 18th February, 2022 during a one day public hearng on the National Electoral Offences Commission (Establishment) Bill 2021 organized by the senate Committee on INECworkshop

⁴ Op cit Omotola, J.S. (2010)

⁵ | FGN 2014

It is therefore, difficult for INEC and other institutions and agencies responsible for the prosecution of electoral law violators to prosecute offenders because the system is built on weak foundation. So, many offenders get away without being punished due to their affiliation with political parties. Attesting to this fact, the late President of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Alhaji Umaru Musa `Yar `Adua after the 2007 General elections admitted that the election that brought him to power was marred by irregularities.

In a nationwide broadcast, he quickly inaugurated a Committee on electoral reform to review electoral process known as Justice Uwais Commission. The effect of these is that there is laxity in the prosecution of electoral law violators and these therefore question the integrity of the elections.

2.0 LAWS ON THE PROSECUTION OF ELECTORAL OFFENCES IN NIGERIA

Lack of prosecution of electoral offences in Nigeria is viewed with seriousness because it creates danger and lack of confidence in elections and its integrity in the minds of the electorates. However successive Governments enacted various laws for the prosecution of crimes including electoral offences in order to curb the menace. These legislations are as follows:

i. THE 1999 CONSTITUTION OF THE FEDERAL REPUBLIC OF NIGERIA (AS AMENDED)

The 1999 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria as amended established the office of the Attorney General of the federation⁹ and that of the states¹⁰ and conferred prosecutorial powers on them. Section 174 (1) of the constitution provides as follows:

“The Attorney General of the federation shall have power to

(a) Institute and undertake criminal proceedings against any person before any court of law in Nigeria other than a court martial in respect of any offence created by or under any Act of the National Assembly;

(b) Take over and continue any such criminal proceedings that may have been instituted by any other authority or person; and

⁹ Section 174 1999 constitution of the federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended)

¹⁰ Section 211 of the said constitution

(c) Discontinue at any stage before judgment is delivered on such criminal proceedings instituted or undertaken by him or any other authority or person.”¹¹

Similar provisions were made regarding the powers of the Attorneys- General of the states.¹²

The Attorney General must carry out the responsibilities of criminal prosecutions independent of partisan political pressure. The objectives of criminal prosecutions must be undertaken and seen to be undertaken on strict objectives and legal criteria free of any political considerations. Whether to initiate or stay criminal proceedings is not an issue of Government policy. The responsibility is a matter of the Attorney- General acting as the constitution’s attorney¹³. Whosoever institutes a criminal proceeding risks the powers of the Attorney-General to take over and continue or discontinue it by entering a *nolle prosqui*. This provision was affirmed by the Supreme Court of Nigeria in the case of *State vs. Akor*.¹⁴ It means here that, any criminal proceedings initiated by any organ, institution or agency of the government even private individuals are subject to the Attorney-General’s powers. For example, in Kwara state during the 2nd Republic, the civilian Governor had disagreement with the state Attorney-General, he removed him. There was a pending case before the chief magistrate court Ilorin against one Isiaka Sanni & 2 ors. who were political supporters of the Governor. The Governor had a brilliant idea and appointed himself as the Attorney - General and Commissioner for justice and consequently signed a purported *nolle prosqui* to free his supporters.¹⁵ Similarly, the Imo state Governor had to remove the Attorney -General, because he abused his power of *nolle prosqui* by terminating a criminal case pending against his clients before he was appointed¹⁶. More recently, reiterating this position, the Supreme Court of Nigeria stated in the case of *SANI V. STATE* (supra):

*“... the Attorney General has at common Law been a master unto himself
And under no control whatsoever, Judicial or otherwise, vis- a-vis his
Powers of instituting or discontinuing criminal proceedings”.*

¹¹ *Sani V. State* (2023) 2 NWLR PT. PT. 167, 77

¹² Section 211 (1) and (2) of the constitution

¹³ Nchi, S.I and Wada, T.U. (2004) powers and Duties of the Attorney General in Nigeria : Greenworld Pub. Co.

¹⁴ (1980) 2NCLR 410

¹⁵ Ekundayi, A.A op cit

¹⁶ New Nigerian Newspaper, Friday, June, 5, 1987, p.1

In another vein the court went further to states that:

“... he is the ultimate authority and custodian of the powers of the state to prosecute...”

ii. THE ELECTORAL ACT, 2022

The Electoral Act, 2022 empowered the legal officers of the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) or any legal officer appointed by it (INEC)¹⁷ to undertake the prosecution of offences committed under the Act. However, the Commission lacks the power to arrest, detain, search and investigate electoral offenders, but the police have these powers to investigate such abuses. The INEC lacks the capacity and power to undertake investigation with a view to gather facts that will be useful in the prosecution of the alleged offenders.¹⁸ The above Electoral Laws are merely paper work document without adequate machinery in place for enforcing them.¹⁹

iii. THE POLICE ACT

The police has the power to arrest and investigate electoral offences; the burden still lies with them to bring the matter properly before a court²⁰ (usually a magistrate court) except a court martial.

The Nigerian police are established by section 214 of the 1999 Constitution which section provides as follows: -

“There shall be a police for Nigeria which shall be known as the Nigeria police Force and subject to the provision of this section no other police force shall be established for the Federation or any part thereof”

Again, section 4 of the police Act provides:

“The powers of the Nigeria police are as set out in these statutes include (iii) apprehension and prosecution of Offenders”

It is beyond doubt that the services of the police are very germane so long as criminal justice must be administered effectively. However, it has been observed with dismay that in some cases, the police tend to abuse their powers or exercise them in most accursed

¹⁷ Section 146 (2) of the Electoral Act 2022

¹⁸ Okoye, F I op cit

¹⁹ Aniekwe, C.C and Kushie, J. (2011) “Electoral Violence Situational Analysis: Identifying Hotspots in the 2011 General Elections in Nigeria” for National Association for peaceful elections in Nigeria.

²⁰ Section 23 police Act, cap P laws of the federation 2004, section 114 CPC, section 78 (b) CPA, Olusemo V. COP (1988) 2 NWLR PT.575,547 and FRN V. Osahon (2006) 2 SC, 11.

procedure due to corruption, petulance or in few cases due to ignorance. This undoubtedly led to miscarriage of justice.²¹

Furthermore, the police are not doing anything to prosecute such offenders, in spite of though, unutilized judicial findings of numerous brutal killings during the last general elections yet no single suspect has been arrested let alone being prosecuted in court by the Nigerian police even when some of the killings in fact took place right inside police station and in the presence of the police and soldiers.²² The police lack the political will and independence to carry out investigations related to electoral offences²³

iv. THE CRIMINAL PROCEDURE CODE AND CRIMINAL PROCEDURE ACT (POWERS OF A PRIVATE PERSON TO PROSECUTE ELECTORAL OFFENCES).

The criminal procedure code which is applicable in the whole of Northern Nigeria and the criminal procedure Act which is applicable in southern Nigeria preserved the right of a private person to prosecute crimes including electoral offences. Any person may institute criminal proceedings against another person unless the law specifically provides that the proceedings in question can only be brought by a particular person or class of persons²⁴. However, these laws were replaced in some states of the federation with the Administration of Criminal Justice Law²⁵ but still the provisions are maintained. Re-emphasizing this position more recently the Supreme Court of Nigeria in *RAPHAEL OBIJAKU V. CHIEF JOE OBIJAKU & 2 OTHERS*²⁶

Aboki, JSC, (as he then was) said: -

“A private legal practitioner or indeed a private citizen has the indisputable right, under section 301(1) of the Anambra State Administration of Criminal

²¹ Nze, I (2007) “police and the Administration of criminal justice” cited in some aspects of law: essays in honor of Chief Obiyera Odunlade, Zenith Publishers.

²² Ahamba, M (2005) “the role of Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) and the Judiciary in the establishment of a sustainable Democracy in Nigeria” A paper delivered at the International Conference on sustainable Democracy in Nigeria: Challenges and prospects organized by the foundation for Good Governance and development in Nigeria held at Imperial College London, south Kensington Campus on 25th June, 2005

²³ [Http://www.hrv.org/en/news/2011/03/13nigeria-pass-bill-prosecute-electoral-abuse?i](http://www.hrv.org/en/news/2011/03/13nigeria-pass-bill-prosecute-electoral-abuse?i)

²⁴ Section 143E CPC and 59 (1) CPA

²⁵ Administration of Criminal justice law, Bauchi state, 2022

²⁶ (2022) 17 NWLR PT. 1857, 377 AT 405, paras E-F

Justice law 2010 to, lay a complaint and prosecute same, without the fiat of the Attorney General of the State”.

*These powers of a private person risk the powers of it being taken over by the Attorney- General”.*²⁷

v. ECONOMIC AND FINANCIAL CRIMES COMMISSION²⁸

In order to further curb the menace of Electoral offences, the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission was established and is conferred with the power to institute criminal proceedings against violators of such acts. However, Section 5 of the Act conferred power on the Commission to investigate such offences as may be conferred on it²⁹. So any person who is suspected to have committed any electoral offences relating to any act to which the Commission is empowered to investigate and prosecute may do so.

vi. ANTI CORRUPTION LAW (INDEPENDENT CORRUPT PRACTICES AND OTHER RELATED OFFENCES ACT) 2000

The Act empowered the prosecutors in the legal department of the Independent Corrupt Practices and other related offences Commission (ICPC) to prosecute offences under the Act upon the delegation of such powers by the Attorney- General of the Federation.³⁰

The Act further established an independent commission³¹ with powers to receive, investigate, and prosecute alleged crimes of corruption and other related offences enumerated in the Act. In the recently concluded National elections the commission (ICPC Commission) arrested a man in possession of N2 Million ferrying it to a politician.³²

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The methodology engaged in any research is dependent on the objective the study seeks to achieve. The methodology adopted in conducting this research is qualitative research method. This method is trustworthy and authentic.³³ The study investigated the topic as if

²⁷ Section 174 (10 (b) and 211 (1) (b) state v. Ilori (supra)

²⁸ Established by the Economic and financial crimes Commission (Establishment) Act, 2002

²⁹ Section 5 (2) (b) of the of the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (Establishment) Act, 2002

³⁰ Section 6 (a) and (61) of the Act

³¹ Section 3

little or nothing is known about the topic investigated. The choice of this technique is in tandem with the study to justify the findings of the paper to be able to draw conclusions.

4.0 FINDINGS

Several issues were raised concerning the laws on prosecution of electoral offences in Nigeria, the followings are the major findings of the work: -

- a) Prosecution of electoral offences is done by the agencies mentioned above.
- b) There are multiplicity of prosecuting agencies and or persons namely; the Attorney –General, INEC, Police, EFCC, ICPC and a Private Person.
- c) The independent National Electoral Commission lacks the power to arrest, detain and investigate persons alleged to have committed the offences.
- d) There is no special unit for investigation of electoral offences
- e) The agencies are reluctant to prosecute electoral law violators
- f) There exist conflicts of interest between the DPP, Police, INEC etc.

5.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1- Establish Electoral Offences Commission and confer on it powers of arrests, detention, search, investigation and prosecution of electoral offences to the exclusion of any other agency and or persons.
- 2- Amend section 150, 174 and 211 of the constitution to separate the office of the Minister of Justice and Attorney General and confer prosecutorial powers to the Director of Public Prosecutions
- 3- Amend sections 145 and 146 (2) of the Electoral Act, 2022 to remove the powers of INEC from prosecuting electoral offences
- 4- Enact a law to transfer to the commission any person arrested who is alleged to have committed electoral offences within 12 hours of arrests.

6.0 CONCLUSION

We conclude by saying the power to prosecute electoral offences as conferred by the extant laws is grossly inadequate. There is the need to implement the above recommendations for effective prosecutions of electoral offenders in order to restore sanity in the polity.